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Zeb1 activation permits entry to the luminal A lineage.

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We describe here activation of the epithelial-mesenchymal transition program factor Zeb1 as a defining characteristic of the luminal A subtype in humans with breast cancer. Zeb1 expression distinguished the luminal A and luminal B subtypes, supporting the concept that silencing of Zeb1 occurs during bifurcation of a luminal progenitor to luminal A and luminal B fates. The data reconcile functions for an EMT factor, activated during transformation, later in subtype selection.